

Various Narrative Forms of Oral Literature of the Monpa Tribe of Tawang District of Arunachal Pradesh

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Abstract

Oral literature encompasses a wide range of cultural expressions transmitted verbally across generations, reflecting a society's values, beliefs, worldview, and historical consciousness. Like other tribes of Arunachal Pradesh, the Monpa tribe of Tawang has preserved its rich cultural heritage primarily through oral traditions, with the exception of religious scriptures, which are documented in the Tibetan (Bhoti) script. The oral literature of the Monpa tribe performs multiple functions, including entertainment, moral and religious instruction, cultural preservation, exploration of human experiences, and explanation of natural phenomena. Since time immemorial, Monpas have orally transmitted folktales, myths, legends, folksongs, proverbs, and other narrative forms to successive generations in order to sustain their cultural identity. These narratives uniquely combine entertainment with ethical and religious teachings while offering insights into the socio-economic and political developments of the community. Each narrative form of Monpa oral literature possesses distinctive structural and thematic characteristics, enabling their classification into various forms. However, rapid technological advancement and modern modes of education and entertainment have raised serious concerns regarding the survival of Monpa storytelling traditions. The younger generation is increasingly losing linguistic competence and cultural engagement, resulting in a gradual erosion of Monpa oral heritage. This paper examines the various narrative forms and characteristics of Monpa oral literature, traces their evolution, and analyses their present deteriorating state. It also explores possible strategies for preservation amidst contemporary challenges. The study adopts a participatory research methodology and is based on first-hand interviews with experienced members of the Monpa community.

Keywords

Oral Literature, Monpa, Cultural Heritage, Folklore, Preservation.

Introduction

The Monpas are one of the twenty-six major tribes of Arunachal Pradesh, distinguished by their unique culture, traditions, and belief systems. They primarily inhabit the picturesque district of Tawang and two subdivisions of West Kameng district—Kalaktang and Dirang. The Monpas predominantly practice Mahayana Buddhism, particularly the Gelug sect, while also retaining elements of their indigenous Bon faith. They are widely known for their traditional stone houses adapted to cold climatic conditions, yak rearing, terrace cultivation, refined handicrafts, and a rich corpus of oral literature.

Although the Monpas share broadly similar socio-religious beliefs, scholars have identified internal distinctions based on dialect, geographical location, and certain cultural traits. Tsewang Norbu (2008) observes that, on the basis of such differences, many writers have broadly classified the Monpas into three groups: Dirang Monpa, Kalaktang Monpa, and Tawang Monpa (p. 23). The Monpas of Dirang and Kalaktang collectively refer to themselves as *Tsangla*, while they identify the Monpas of Tawang as *Brami*. Conversely, the Tawang Monpas refer to the Monpas of Dirang and Kalaktang as *Shershokpa*, meaning "people of the east." The Monpas inhabiting the present Dirang region are also known as *Drangnangpa*, while those of the Kalaktang region are referred to as *Rongnangpa*, names derived from the rivers flowing through their respective regions. Among these groups, the Tawang Monpas are numerically the largest (Norbu, 2008).

The present study focuses specifically on the oral literature of the Tawang Monpas, examining its nature, narrative forms, and the gradual decline of its transmission. Like other tribal communities, Monpa folktales document the historical evolution of the community, preserving narratives related to origin, migration from Mongoloid racial groups, cultural traditions, religious beliefs, and collective identity. Similar to many tribes of Arunachal Pradesh, the Monpas do not possess an indigenous script for their dialect; instead, the Bhoti (Tibetan) script is used for religious texts and important documentation.

Owing to their close religious and cultural association with Tibetan Buddhism, many Monpa folktales—particularly those with strong religious themes—are derived from Tibetan sacred narratives. *Namthar* (or *Namtar*), meaning spiritual biography or hagiography in Tibetan Buddhism, forms the foundation of several prominent Monpa folktales. One historically significant *Namthar*, supported by material and institutional evidence, is associated with the Mon region of both Tawang district (Tawang Monastery, Pungteng, Zemithang) and

West Kameng district (Lhagyalo Gompa). This narrative recounts the story of Dakini Khando Drowa Zangmo and King Kalawangpo of Tawang. Most *Namthar* texts are documented in Bhoti and require interpretation by individuals proficient in both Monpa and Tibetan languages.

Objective of study

The objectives of the present study are:

1. To examine the various narrative forms of Monpa oral literature.
2. To investigate the present condition and challenges faced by Monpa folktales.
3. To identify possible methods for the preservation of Monpa oral traditions.

Review of Literature

The study of oral literature occupies a central position in folklore, anthropology, and literary studies. Milman Parry and Albert Lord argue that oral traditions are complex artistic systems governed by culturally specific rules of composition and performance (Parry, 1971; Lord, 2000). Oral narratives function as dynamic texts that are continually recreated through performance, memory, and communal participation.

Walter J. Ong (1982) conceptualizes orality as a distinct mode of thought characterized by repetition, formulaic expression, and reliance on shared cultural knowledge. These features are evident in Monpa oral literature, where folktales (*Tam*), riddles, proverbs, and folksongs are embedded in ritual practice and social interaction. Storytelling among the Monpas thus remains a communal and performative act rather than a fixed textual transmission.

From a functionalist perspective, William R. Bascom (1954) identifies four primary functions of folklore: entertainment, validation of culture, education, and maintenance of social conformity. Monpa oral narratives fulfill all these functions. While *Shop Tam* primarily serves as an entertainment function, *Choe Tam* and *Sem-gyurmey Tam* reinforce Buddhist ethics and moral values. Proverbs (*Khabshey*) and riddles operate as informal pedagogical tools transmitting indigenous knowledge.

Jan Vansina (1985) emphasizes the historical significance of oral traditions, arguing that they serve as legitimate sources for reconstructing the past of non-literate societies. In the Monpa context, folktales preserve collective memory related to migration, religious institutions, and social organization. *Namthar* narratives, in particular, blur the boundaries between history, mythology, and religion.

Methodology

The study adopts a participatory research methodology. Primary data were collected through in-depth interviews with elderly and knowledgeable members of the Monpa community who possess extensive experience in oral storytelling and traditional practices.

Analysis**Folktales of the Monpa**

Monpa oral literature comprises folktales, myths (both functional and cosmogonic), legends, riddles, proverbs, folksongs, and narratives in prose and verse. These diverse narrative forms collectively serve as primary epistemological sources for understanding the customs, belief systems, social values, and worldview of the Monpa community. An important exception within Monpa oral literature is the longer narratives known as *Namthar*, which are documented in the Tibetan language. However, much of their performative and cultural essence undergoes transformation when orally translated into the Monpa dialect. Consequently, Monpa folktales may be defined as traditional narratives that have been passed down orally through generations within a community.

All narrative forms of Monpa oral literature serve as vital sources for understanding the customs, traditions, and worldview of the community. In the Monpa dialect, the term *Tam* refers collectively to all folktales. Although Monpa oral literature share common features such as moral instruction, religious teachings, and entertainment, they can be broadly categorized based on content and context into the following types:

i) Choe Tam

Choe Tam refers to tales that deal primarily with religious themes. Most *Namthar* narratives fall under this category, as they are spiritual biographies of revered figures in Tibetan Buddhism. Examples include *Choegyri Norzang*, *Ling Gyesser Gyalpo*, *Khandu Drowa Zangmo*, *Sey Dharmalutu*, and legends associated with *Gyalwa Tsangyang Gyatso*, the Sixth Dalai Lama.

ii) Sem-gyurmey Tam

These tales convey moral lessons through protagonists who function as “everyman” figures, embodying universal human qualities, struggles, and experiences. Such narratives reflect collective human aspirations and ethical dilemmas. Examples include *Tsongpon Norbu Zangpo*, *Lounp Rikpachan*, *Zigtsen Milarepa*, and *Leka Drebu*.

iii) Shop Tam

Shop Tam consists of humorous tales narrated primarily for entertainment during leisure time, often among peers. Despite their light-hearted nature, these narratives are not devoid of moral elements. Examples include *Naa Pun Nai*, *Gyep Nai Changan*, and *Brokpa Shorbum*.

iv) Mik Wale-Wale / Zapchekhaw-khaw (Riddles)

Riddles serve as an important form of entertainment and cultural preservation among the Monpas. Traditionally exchanged during communal gatherings in the evenings, riddles foster social interaction and intellectual engagement across generations. They also offer insights into the socio-economic life of the community. Examples include:

1. A fist pointed towards the sky—What is it? (Finger millet)
2. In a white *gompa*, a yellow monk is sitting—What is it? (An egg)
3. When going upwards he has nothing, but when coming downwards he has a long tail—Who is he? (A man carrying bamboo)

Khabshey (Proverbs)

Khabshey reflect the emotional depth, wisdom, and ethical values of the Monpa people. Rooted in lived experience rather than abstract reasoning, these proverbs express social attitudes and moral conduct. Examples include:

1. *Speaking excessively harms others, while performing good deeds benefits oneself. Comment:* This proverb emphasizes compassion and altruism as core Monpa values.
2. *Vintage wine is good for health, and vintage tales are good for the soul. Comment:* This highlights the cultural significance of oral tradition in Monpa society.
3. *People become good in good company and bad in bad company. Comment:* Moral character is shaped by social surroundings, a belief strongly upheld in Monpa culture.

vi) Folksongs (Sama)

Folksongs play a vital role in Monpa social and ritual life and are often accompanied by masked dances and rhythmic movements. Major forms include:

1. *Rigshung Sama* (traditional songs)
2. *Khadon* (prayer and ritual songs)
3. *Darshay* (nuptial songs)
4. *Sholin* (duel songs between lovers)
5. *Namthar Sama* (narrative songs)

Folktales in the Modern Age

Language plays a crucial role in the transmission of oral literature. However, the younger generation of Monpas is experiencing a linguistic shift due to the dominance of digital and non-native languages. This decline in dialectal proficiency has significantly weakened the intergenerational transmission of oral traditions (Finnegan, 2012). Modern education and lifestyle changes have further contributed to cultural alienation among Monpa youth, eroding traditional storytelling practices.

Preservation of Folktales

Immediate measures are required to preserve Monpa Oral Literature. Revitalizing the Monpa dialect, encouraging storytelling practices, documenting folktales, translating Tibetan texts, and utilizing digital platforms are essential strategies. Intergenerational dialogue and creative adaptations, such as animated folklore, can help sustain cultural continuity.

Conclusion

Monpa folktales constitute an invaluable source for understanding the historical evolution and cultural identity of the Monpa community. Despite their thematic diversity, all narrative forms emphasize compassion, ethical conduct, and harmonious living—principles deeply rooted in Buddhist philosophy. Systematic documentation, linguistic preservation, and scholarly engagement are essential to safeguard the oral heritage of the Monpa tribe for future generations.

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